

Barrier-free microfluidic paper analytical devices for multiplex colorimetric detection of analytes

Ayushi Chauhan, Bhushan J. Toley*

Department of Chemical Engineering
Indian Institute of Science
Bangalore, India

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*Correspondence to:

Bhushan J. Toley
Department of Chemical Engineering
Indian Institute of Science Bangalore
Malleswaram
Bangalore 560012
Phone: +91-9146142296
Email: bhushan@iisc.ac.in

Addresses of other contributing authors:

Ayushi Chauhan
Department of Chemical Engineering
Indian Institute of Science Bangalore
Malleswaram
Bangalore 560012

Abstract

In recent years, microfluidic paper analytical devices (μ PADs) have been extensively utilized to conduct multiplex colorimetric assays. Despite their simple and user-friendly operation, the need for patterning paper with wax or other physical barriers to create flow channels makes large scale manufacturing cumbersome. Moreover, convection of rehydrated reagents in the test zones leads to non-uniform colorimetric signals, which makes quantification challenging. To overcome these challenges, we present a device called barrier-free μ PAD (BF- μ PAD) that consists of a stack of two paper membranes having different wicking rates – the top layer acting as a fluid distributing layer and the bottom layer containing reagents for colorimetric detection. Multiple analytes can be detected using this assembly without the need to pattern either layer with wax or other barriers. In one embodiment, a device is capable of delivering the sample fluid to 20 distinct dried reagent spots stored on an 8cm x 2cm membrane in as few as 30 seconds. The multiplexing feature of BF- μ PAD is demonstrated for colorimetric detection of salivary thiocyanate, protein, glucose, and nitrite. Most importantly, the device improves the limit of detection of colorimetric assays performed on conventional μ PADs by more than 3.5x. To understand fluid imbibition in the paper assembly, the device geometry is modelled in COMSOL Multiphysics using Richards equation; the results obtained provide insights into the non-intuitive flow pattern producing perfectly uniform signals in the barrier-free assembly.

Introduction

Microfluidic paper analytical devices (μ PADs) have become a powerful tool for point-of-care (POC) diagnosis owing to their portability, user-friendliness, biodegradability, compatibility with biological fluids, and the ability to store dried reagents¹. One of the most popular applications of μ PADs has been the multiplexed colorimetric detection of analytes in a sample fluid^{1,2}. Detection of multiple analytes is performed by patterning hydrophobic barriers on the membrane to create flow channels, a technique first demonstrated by Martinez et al.³ Multiple techniques have since been utilized for the creation of such barriers, e.g. wax printing, inkjet printing, photolithography, chemical modification of paper etc.; these techniques have been well reviewed by Cate et al.²

Despite their popularity, the techniques used for patterning paper require specialized equipment that increase the cost of fabrication. Further, each technique has associated limitations, e.g. low print resolution in wax printing and inkjet printing, and the need for a clean room, UV exposure facility, and skilled personnel for photolithography techniques. An alternative to patterning is to precisely cut the paper membrane in the desired shape⁴. But this method limits the smallest features that can be created because of limitations of mechanical stability. In addition to cumbersome fabrication processes, the problem of slow flow rate and imperfect mixing leading to non-uniform colorimetric signals⁵ remain the major challenges for multiplex colorimetric detection in μ PADs.

In this article, we introduce a new device design called barrier-free microfluidic paper analytical device (BF- μ PAD) that can simultaneously detect multiple targets without patterning barriers in paper. This was enabled by stacking two paper membranes with significantly different wicking rates. The top layer having a high wicking rate is used as a sample fluid

distributor, and detection reagents are spotted on the bottom membrane having a low wicking rate. The large difference in wicking rates ensures that the flow of sample fluid to the detection zones is predominantly in the vertical direction, from the top to the bottom membrane. Further, lateral flow in the bottom membrane is practically eliminated, obviating the need for barriers, and producing highly spatially uniform colorimetric signals. Our group has previously demonstrated the application of such an assembly in uniform rehydration of sample stabilization reagents stored on the bottom membrane, which aided in effective sample stabilization⁶. To better understand flow patterns in such an assembly, we present a Richards equation model of wicking flow in this stacked assembly. Richards equation⁷ accounts for partial saturation in paper membranes and our group^{8,9} and others^{10,11} have previously established its use in modelling flow in paper microfluidic devices. We demonstrate the multiplexing feature of BF- μ PAD by simultaneously testing four analytes thiocyanate¹², protein³, glucose^{4,13}, and nitrite^{14,15} in a 2cm x 2cm assembly. The barrier free assembly presented here overcomes important limitations of current single layer barrier-patterned μ PADs.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials and fabrication

Standard 17 glass fiber (referred to as ‘Standard 17’ here onward) and Whatman filter paper Grade 1 (referred to as ‘filter paper’ here onward) membranes were acquired from GE Healthcare Life Sciences (Bangalore, India). Transparent acrylic sheets of thickness 2.16 mm and 5 mm were acquired locally. All layered devices were fabricated using 2.16 mm acrylic sheets and circular fluid reservoirs were cut into 5 mm acrylic sheets. Double-sided pressure sensitive adhesive (PSA; 3M 9731) and PDMS tape (ARclad IS-7876) were used to secure the paper layers and acrylic sheets together. All designs were created in AutoCAD (Autodesk, San

Rafael, CA). All materials were cut using a 50 W CO₂ laser in a VLS 3.60 laser engraver (Universal Laser Systems, Scottsdale, AZ). Images were captured using a Redmi 5 smartphone and a Canon LiDE 220 flatbed scanner.

Chemicals and assays

All reagents and stock solutions were prepared in DI water unless otherwise mentioned. pH experiments were performed using 10 mg/ml bromophenol blue solution (Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. India) as the indicator and 1 M HCl (Thomas Baker Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.) as the sample fluid. Colorimetric assays were adapted from literature: the thiocyanate detection assay from Pena-Pereira et al.¹², the protein detection assay from Martinez et al.³, glucose detection assay from Zhu et al.⁴ and Santana-Jimenez et al.¹³, and the nitrite detection assay from Klasner et al.¹⁴ and Blicharz et al.¹⁵. Details of all assays are provided in Supporting Information (SI) Section 1. For paper-based assays, reagents were manually pipetted on the paper and dried for 15 min followed by device assembly and immediate introduction of sample.

Image analysis and determination of limits of detection

All images were analyzed in ImageJ software. Color images (8-bit) were first split into red, blue, and green channels. For the pH experiment and thiocyanate assay, signal intensities were measured using the blue channel; for glucose and nitrite assays using the green channel; and for protein assay using the red channel. A circular region of interest (ROI) covering ~80% of the diameter of the signal was created to measure the mean intensity, I , of a signal spot; the size of the ROI was fixed for all analyses. The blank signal, I_{blank} , measured as the mean (N=3) of the signal intensity generated by introducing DI water into identical detection zones was subtracted from all test signals. Prior to subtraction, all intensities were inverted by subtracting from 255 to account for generation of colored spots over a white background. Final signal

intensities were thus reported as $I_{test} = (255 - I) - (255 - I_{blank})$. The limits of detection for BF- μ PAD and μ PAD were calculated using a 4-parameter logistic curve described by Holstein et al¹⁶. The method includes variance of mean of all data points performed in replicates (N=4) for 7 different analyte concentrations including the blank.

MODELLING SECTION

To understand fluid flow profiles in BF- μ PAD, the device was modelled in COMOSL Multiphysics 5.4 software using Richards equation using methods previously described by our group^{8,9}:

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\kappa(\theta)}{\mu} \nabla (\psi(\theta) + \rho g z) \right) \text{-----}(1)$$

where θ is volumetric liquid content in the membrane, ψ is capillary pressure (Pa) induced by the membrane on the liquid, κ is permeability (m^2) of the membrane, and μ is viscosity (Pa.s) of the liquid. Because the assembly was kept horizontal and the membranes were very thin ($\sim 10^{-4}$ m), gravitational head $\rho g z$ was neglected. A normalized saturation parameter was defined as $Se = (\theta - \theta_r) / (\theta_s - \theta_r)$, where θ_s is the maximum volumetric content at saturation, and θ_r is the residual volumetric content (assumed to be 0). θ varies from θ_r to θ_s and therefore Se varies from 0 to 1. In order to solve the Richards equation, ψ and κ as a function of Se must be known for each porous material. A popular set of constitutive relations for $\kappa(Se)$ and $\psi(Se)$ is the Van Genuchten formulation that involves three parameters: α, n, l for each material. These parameters were obtained by fitting experimental data for $\psi(Se)$ for Standard 17 and filter paper previously acquired in our lab⁶. Details of the Van Genuchten formulation and all parameters used for COMSOL simulations are provided in SI Section 2.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Design and function of BF- μ PAD

BF- μ PAD consists of a stack of a Standard 17 membrane placed flush on top of a filter paper membrane (Fig. 1A). Reagents for analyte detection are spotted at distinct locations in the filter paper membrane and the sample fluid is added on top of the Standard 17 membrane (Fig. 1A). The top Standard 17 layer has a higher wicking rate compared to the bottom filter paper layer. The $T_{4\text{-cm}}$, i.e. time required for fluid to wick 4 cm from the source in horizontally placed membrane strips, are 11.3 ± 1.15 s and 110 ± 13 s for Standard 17 and filter paper, respectively⁶.

Prior to multiplex detection, an 8 cm x 2 cm BF- μ PAD was tested for uniformity of signals over the surface by depositing multiple spots of a pH dye on the detection layer (Fig. 1A). Sixteen 1 μ l spots of 10 mg/ml bromophenol blue were hand pipetted on the detection layer using a custom-made 8 cm x 2 cm acrylic stencil containing equispaced holes of 0.6 mm radius. The generated spots were allowed to dry for 15 minutes at room temperature before placing the Standard 17 distribution layer on top. PSA layers, 8 cm x 2 cm, were used to adhere the detection layer to the bottom acrylic base and to adhere the distribution layer to the top acrylic cover. The top acrylic cover and the top PSA layer had 4 mm radius holes at the center for sample introduction. The entire assembly was secured with PDMS tape along the longer edges to prevent fluid leakage. A fluid reservoir made out of acrylic was adhered on the top acrylic cover. The top and bottom acrylic layers had small protrusions on both ends (Fig. 1A) to enable supporting the device at an elevation to enable imaging from both sides.

A direct comparison of colorimetric signal development in BF- μ PADs and control devices was performed. A control device consisted of a single 8 cm x 2 cm filter paper detection layer spotted identically with reagents but lacking the top distributor layer (Fig. 1B). For this, a 1 M

HCl solution was introduced into both: 255 μl in control and 895 μl in BF- μPAD . These volumes were chosen to match the fluid absorption capacities of the respective devices. On addition of acid, the blue pH indicator changes color to yellow. When HCl was added to control, by the time the fluid fully wet the membrane ($t = 150\text{s}$), the yellow spots merged into each other generating smudges of yellow color (Fig. 1B; Control). However, the BF- μPAD generated 16 distinct signal spots (Fig. 1B; BF- μPAD), even though the detection regions were not separated by physical barriers. Further, the time of rehydration reduced to 30s owing to the rapid wicking rate of the distribution layer. The smudges in control are explained by the laterally wicking fluid pushing (convecting) the dried reagents along with it. On the other hand, in BF- μPAD , the lateral flow primarily occurs in the distribution layer; there is practically zero lateral flow in the bottom detection layer. These flow patterns are modelled in the following section.

The uniformity of signal across all 16 spots in the BF- μPAD was then assessed. Fig. 1C shows the mean intensity of the 16 spots when imaged from the bottom (detection layer side) using a flatbed scanner (empty squares; Fig. 1C) and a smartphone camera (solid circles; Fig. 1C). Error bars represent standard deviations in mean intensities at each spot location across three replicates of the device. There was no statistically significant difference in the mean intensity across the 16 spots, which confirms that the performance of a detection spot is not dependent on its distance from the fluid source. Coefficients of variation in mean intensity of all 48 spots across 3 replicate devices were 6.94% when imaged by a smartphone and 3.49% when imaged using a flatbed scanner. While demonstrated using 16 detection spots here, an 8 cm x 2 cm BF- μPAD can also incorporate 20 reagent spots of 1 μl each of pH dye (SI Section S3 and Movie S1) and 32 reagent spots of 0.4 μl each of glucose assay (SI section S3 and Movie S2).

Figure 1. Design and function of BF- μ PAD. **(A)** Schematic of an 8 cm x 2 cm device containing 16 detection zones. **(B)** Comparison of rehydrated reagents with and without the distribution layer, on addition of 1M HCl. In control, rehydrated reagents merge into each other; in BF- μ PAD, all 16 rehydrated reagent spots remain segregated. **(C)** End-point color intensities of the 16 detection spots in BF- μ PAD for images captured by a smartphone and a flatbed scanner. Error bars represent standard deviations (N=3).

Modelling flow in an assembly of Standard 17 and filter paper

Wicking flow in an assembly of a Standard 17 layer placed on top of a filter paper membrane was modelled using Richards equation to understand flow patterns. Our group has previously demonstrated the use of Richards equation in modeling wicking flow through a serial assembly of two different membranes⁹. However, this is the first demonstration of the use of Richards equation for modelling flow through a stack of paper membranes. For this, a 2D spatial domain is considered – x direction being the direction of lateral flow along the length of the device, and y direction being the vertical direction spanning the thickness of the two membranes (Fig. 2A). Because the flow profile would be uniform around the central fluid reservoir, only half of the device was modelled, representing a side view of the assembly (Fig. 2A). The top rectangle

(or domain) represents the 370 μm thick Standard 17 distribution layer and the bottom rectangle represents the 180 μm thick filter paper detection layer (Fig. 2A). Fluid inlet was represented by a 4 mm horizontal line at $y = 0$, initiating from the origin. Note that the representation of the domain in Fig. 2A is not to scale.

The Richards equation solves for Se , the normalized saturation, as a function of space and time. Initial and boundary conditions were similar to what were used in our group's previous publications and are provided in SI Section 2. After solving the model for Se over space and time, convective velocity was calculated as⁹:

$$velocity = \frac{\kappa(\theta)}{\mu} \nabla(\psi(\theta)) \text{-----}(2)$$

Horizontal (u) and vertical (v) velocity components in the two domains were extracted using 6 spatial points – 1, 2, and 3 cm from the origin in the x direction, and at the centers of the two domains in the y direction (-185 μm and -460 μm for top and bottom domain, respectively; Fig. 2A). In the top domain, horizontal velocity, u , decreased over time for all three spatial points (Washburn-like behavior), ultimately reaching zero at full membrane saturation (Fig. 2B(i)). On the other hand, the vertical velocity, v , at all three points in the top domain was ephemeral and appeared as sharp spikes at time points when the fluid fronts reached those spatial points (Fig. 2B(ii)). Moreover, the magnitudes of v were ~ 1 order of magnitude lower than that of u (Fig. 2B (i)-(ii)). These spikes in vertical velocity, v , represent movement of the fluid from the top to the bottom domain and their short durations suggest that the membranes saturate rapidly in vertical direction. A similar analysis was conducted for the chosen spatial points in the bottom membrane. In stark contrast to the top domain, the horizontal velocity, u , in the bottom domain only appeared as spikes (Fig. 2B(iii)). Vertical velocities, v , in the bottom domain reflect those in the top domain and also appear as spikes (Fig. 2B(iv)) with peak velocities being ~ 1 order of magnitude less than horizontal velocities, u . Two important observations may

be made from these data: a) the dominant direction of flow in the assembly is the horizontal direction, and b) there is no continuous flow of fluid in any direction in the bottom membrane. These observations were corroborated by a direct comparison of horizontal velocities, u , in the top and bottom domains along horizontal lines ($x = 0$ to 4 cm) at $y = -185 \mu\text{m}$ (top domain) and $y = -460 \mu\text{m}$ (bottom domain) (Fig. 2C). Velocities were extracted at three different time points – 5s, 10s, and 15s. In the top domain, non-zero velocities existed all the way up to the fluid fronts (solid lines; left y-axis; Fig. 2C), while in the bottom domain, non-zero velocities existed only locally in the vicinity of the fluid fronts (dotted lines; right y-axis; Fig. 2C). Further, the magnitude of horizontal velocity was about an order of magnitude higher in the top domain compared to bottom (left vs right y-axis; Fig. 2C). Surface plots of horizontal velocity, u , at different time points ($t = 0.5\text{s}$, 2.5s , 7s , and 13s) shed more light on the flow patterns (Fig. 2D). While the top domain contained large regions having a significant convective velocity at any time, the bottom domain only had local regions of convection just below the fluid fronts in the top domain. Further, these local convective velocities are temporary (Fig. 2B(iii)-(iv)).

Figure 2. Results of flow modelling. **(A)** Model geometry representing side view of BF- μ PAD with a 4 mm horizontal line at $y=0$ as the fluid inlet. **(B)** Comparison of horizontal (u) and vertical (v) velocity components at three different x locations along the centers of membrane thicknesses for top domain (**i**, **ii**) and bottom domain (**iii**, **iv**). **(C)** Variation of lateral flow velocity along 4 cm horizontal lines passing through the centers of membrane thicknesses at three different time points. **(D)** Surface plots of horizontal velocity profiles at different time points.

From these results, the following can be concluded about wicking flow in the BF- μ PAD assembly. Fluid introduced into the top layer wicks rapidly away from the source in the lateral direction and continuously feeds fluid to the bottom layer in the vertical direction. As soon as the bottom layer receives fluid, it saturates and there is no more movement of fluid in the

bottom layer. Instead, the unsaturated regions of the bottom membrane continue to receive fluid from the top distribution layer. This explains why rehydrated reagents in the detection layer of BF- μ PAD do not move away from their locations via convection, enabling barrier-free multiplex detection. Note that diffusion of rehydrated reagents would still occur in the bottom domain and could carry reagents away from the detection zones, but the time scale for diffusion is significantly longer than the test time; within the time span of the detection experiment (< 6 min), diffusion over these length scales may be safely neglected.

Multiplex detection in BF- μ PAD

The application of BF- μ PAD for multiplex colorimetric detection is demonstrated next using a 2 cm x 2 cm device containing 4 analyte detection zones, prepared by manually pipetting 1 μ l each of the corresponding colorimetric detection reagent. The user experience is shown in Fig. 3A; the user is required to add a predefined sample volume equal to volumetric capacity of the two membranes into the sample reservoir (244 μ l for a 2 cm x 2 cm device), wait for 30 seconds for the sample to saturate the assembly and develop signal, and flip the device to image the bottom layer using a smartphone. Multiplexing is demonstrated using four clinically relevant analytes: thiocyanate (SCN^-), protein (BSA), glucose, and nitrite (NO_2^-)^{3,4,12-15}. While all these analytes are adequately present in saliva, the demonstration here uses samples prepared in DI water. However, our group has previously demonstrated that such a stacked assembly is compatible with flow of more viscous fluids like sputum⁶. Eight different samples having varying concentrations of the 4 analytes were prepared. Concentrations were chosen such that they spanned the clinically relevant range of these analytes in saliva. Fig. 3B shows an actual fabricated BF- μ PAD device before sample addition, along with the locations of the four detection reagents. The SCN^- reagent turns colorless to brown, glucose and NO_2^- reagents turn colorless to pink, and the BSA reagent changes from yellow to blue with increasing analyte

concentration. Results of detection from 8 different samples containing SCN^- ion and glucose concentrations in decreasing order and BSA and NO_2^- ion concentration in increasing order (from top to bottom row) are shown in Fig. 3C. Four distinct reaction zones were maintained throughout the test. The intensity of color generated over the circular ROI for each analyte increased monotonously with increasing analyte concentration (Fig. 3D).

Figure 3. Multiplex detection in BF- μ PAD. **(A)** The user experience: the user adds the sample into the reservoir, waits for 30s, flips the device and captures the result using a smartphone. **(B)** Image of BF- μ PAD with dried reagents before sample addition. **(C)** Results from BF- μ PAD after introduction of samples containing different concentrations of 4 analytes: thiocyanate, BSA, glucose, and nitrite. Black circle around 40 mg/dl glucose shows the representative ROI for signal analysis. **(D)** Calibration plots for thiocyanate, nitrite, BSA, and glucose. Error bars represent standard deviations ($N=3$).

Investigation on cross-mixing

Because BF- μ PADs lack flow barriers in between detection zones, it was important to determine whether reagents from one detection zone affected colorimetric signals in another

detection zone directly downstream the convective flow. For this, two types of 4 cm x 2 cm BF- μ PADs were fabricated – a singleplex device with 4 nitrite detection spots at four corners (Fig. 4A; singleplex device) and a multiplex device containing 2 spots each for glucose and BSA detection, in addition to the 4 nitrite detection spots (Fig. 4A; multiplex device). In the multiplex device, the nitrite-containing sample introduced into the sample reservoir must flow over the region containing detection zones for BSA and glucose. Solutions containing 4 different nitrite ion concentrations and one blank solution were added as a sample fluid to both devices. The signal intensity of nitrite detection zones increased monotonously with increasing nitrite ion concentration and the signal response was identical for the singleplex and multiplex device (Fig. 4B). Student's t-test comparison of signal intensities for singleplex vs multiplex devices at all nitrite concentration produced P values > 0.41 (N=4), showing that the signals were virtually indistinguishable. It may be noted that the developed pink color for different nitrite concentrations in this experiment was visibly darker than the corresponding pink color produced in the previous multiplex detection experiment (Fig. 3C). This is because the nitrite assay develops signal slowly and, in this analysis, we waited for the color to fully develop and captured images after 6 minutes of sample addition. The longer wait time ensured that enough time was provided for cross reactivity between reagent zones to occur, if any. However, no cross reactivity was found. In a separate set of experiments, the specificity of the colorimetric assays within paper were tested to check whether the presence of multiple analytes in the sample affected the performance of any particular colorimetric assay (SI Section 4). No such interference was found.

Figure 4. Investigations of reagent cross mixing in BF- μ PAD. **(A)** Test results from a singleplex BF- μ PAD containing detection spots for nitrite, and from a multiplex BF- μ PAD containing detection spots for BSA, glucose, and nitrite. Top row: schematic; middle and bottom rows: results from blank and 0.6 mM NO_2^- solution, respectively. **(B)** Variation of mean intensity with NO_2^- concentration in singleplex and multiplex devices. Error bars represent standard deviations (N=4).

Comparative performance of BF- μ PAD and μ PAD

The performance of the colorimetric assay for the detection of BSA in a 4-zone BF- μ PAD (Fig. 5A; top row) was compared to that in a conventional single layer μ PAD made from filter paper (Fig. 5B; bottom row). The single layer μ PADs tested here did not contain wax or hydrophobic barriers; instead flow channels were created by cutting the desired paper shapes using a laser cutter (Fig. 5B; bottom row). These devices replicate the flow patterns and rehydration profiles found in conventional wax patterned single layer μ PADs. Dimensions of the laser cut μ PADs are provided in SI section 4. Sample solutions containing six different BSA concentrations were introduced into the two types of devices – μ PADs and BF- μ PADs. Sample volumes were 22 μ l and 244 μ l for μ PADs and BF- μ PADs, respectively, chosen to match the volumetric

capacities of the two devices. Images were acquired using a smartphone camera, 6 minutes after sample introduction. When 0.1 mg/ml and 0.2 mg/ml BSA were added to μ PAD, the signals were undistinguishable from blank (0 mg/ml BSA; Fig. 5A; bottom row), whereas when these samples were added in BF- μ PAD, faint but distinguishable blue color was generated (Fig. 5A; top row). Further, at all concentrations, blue color in single layer μ PADs only developed near the inlet to the detection zone, producing non-homogeneous signals over the circular detection zones (Fig. 5A; bottom row). On the contrary, homogeneous colorimetric signals were generated at all concentrations in BF- μ PAD (Fig. 5A; top row). Uniformity in signals in BF- μ PAD is a result of rehydration of the reagents in the vertical direction from the distribution layer and a near absence of convection in the bottom detection layer.

A direct comparison of the limits of detection (LODs) for the two devices was then performed using the method described by Holstein et al¹⁶. Detailed calculations of LOD are provided in supporting information (SI section 5). For the BSA assay performed in BF- μ PAD, the LOD and corresponding 95% confidence interval (CI) were found to be 0.1817 and 0.1283-0.3682 mg/ml, respectively calculated. For the same assay performed in μ PAD, the LOD and corresponding 95% confidence interval were found to be 0.6727 and 0.5314-0.8217, respectively. BF- μ PADs thus improved the LOD by 3.7x compared to single layer μ PADs. Fig. 5B shows the variation of signal intensity with BSA concentration, and LOD and 95% CI for BF- μ PAD and μ PAD. This improvement in LOD is, at least in part, because of the ability of BF- μ PAD to probe a larger volume of sample residing in the combination of the two layers. At low analyte concentrations, analyte molecules are limiting while the detection reagent molecules are in excess. By enabling the detection reagents to interact with a greater number of analyte molecules in the combination of two layers in BF- μ PAD, more product is formed

and therefore the LOD improves. This advantage may be lost at higher analyte concentrations where the analyte may no longer be limiting (Fig. 5B; 2 mg/ml BSA).

Figure 5. Comparison of LODs between BF-μPAD and μPAD. **(A)** End point images of BF-μPAD and μPAD at different BSA concentrations. **(B)** Variation of mean color intensities with BSA concentration in BF-μPAD and μPAD. Error bars represent standard deviations (N=4).

Overall, we have demonstrated a new paper-based device design that enables multiplex colorimetric detection from fluid samples without patterning paper with physical barriers. While BF-μPADs improve LODs compared to conventional μPADs, they require larger sample volumes, which may be a shortcoming. But for several sample types like saliva, urine, wastewater, food and beverages etc., larger sample volumes are readily available. BF-μPAD is based on a strategic combination of two porous membranes that produce a desired flow pattern. While different combinations of paper materials^{6,17} and combinations of papers with ducts^{18,19} have been developed for manipulating flow rates in paper channels, their utilization for

multiplex colorimetric detection is first demonstrated in this article. An important advantage of BF- μ PAD over conventional μ PADs is that it would be more compatible with viscous fluids and emulsions like milk etc., which are difficult to flow through cellulosic membranes alone. The Standard 17 layer in BF- μ PADs has a significantly larger permeability and enables the flow of viscous fluids as our group has previously demonstrated⁶.

In this work, reagents were manually deposited using a plastic stencil to guide the pipette to desired locations, which led to inconsistent shapes and sizes of reaction zones. However, this issue can easily be overcome using automated reagent dispensers, which are readily available. Out of the 4 colorimetric assays, three assays generated self-contained circular colorimetric signals, but the thiocyanate assay produced signals that spread outside the detection zone (Fig. 3C). This is likely because the thiocyanate assay generates color instantaneously and some colored product diffuses back into the top layer where it moves by convection. The other three colorimetric reactions were slower and took of the order of 2-5 minutes for the color to fully develop, by which time, there was no more convection in the top layer. This puts a theoretical limit on the types of assays that can be incorporated in BF- μ PAD for generation of self-contained signals – the rate of reaction must be slower than the rate of convection in the distribution layer. However, if this is not possible, assays that generate color instantaneously must be placed at the corners of the device, so the colored product does not convect into downstream reaction zones.

CONCLUSION

The BF- μ PAD design overcomes two important limitations of existing μ PADs while improving upon the LODs – i) the need to pattern paper with physical barriers like wax, and ii) spatially non-uniform colorimetric signal generation. Obviating the need to pattern physical

barriers will significantly reduce the infrastructure associated with manufacturing of paper-based analytical devices. The only instrument needed to manufacture BF- μ PADs at a large scale would be a benchtop reagent dispensing robot that can handle microliter volumes, which are widely available commercially. Our future work on the development of BF- μ PAD would include systematically studying combinations of distributor and detection layer materials for optimized performance, testing compatibility with viscous samples, and deployment of BF- μ PADs for field testing.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. The following Supplementary Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

S1: Colorimetric assays S2: COMSOL modelling details; S3: uniform rehydration of 20 spots on a BF- μ PAD; S4: Effect of competing ions on signal intensity; S5: Comparison of signal intensity in BF- μ PAD and μ PAD. (PDF document).

Rehydration of 20 detection spots (Movie S1)

Rehydration of 32 detection spots (Movie S2)

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding author

*E-mail: bhushan@iisc.ac.in. Phone: +91-80-2293-3114.

Author Contributions

B.J.T contributed towards conception and design of the work, obtaining funding, and analysis and interpretation of data. A.C conducted all experiments and contributed towards design of the work and analysis and interpretation of data. B.J.T and A.C together wrote the main manuscript text and prepared figures.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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